

Tool Evaluation Protocols and Prompt Template

Version: 2.0

Protocol version date: May 27, 2026

Part 1: Comparative Tool Evaluation Protocols

1.1 Overview

This document describes the standardized evaluation protocols used to benchmark PubChat against eight state-of-the-art AI tools for systematic literature retrieval. The benchmarking study was designed to ensure fair, reproducible comparison across tools with fundamentally different interaction paradigms.

- **Scope: Nine tools (11 configurations) were evaluated: PubChat in three retrieval modes (Broad, Standard, Core), four Deep Research LLMs (ChatGPT, Gemini, Grok, Qwen), one search-augmented retrieval tool (Perplexity), and three specialized retrieval tools (Elicit, Consensus, ASTA).**
- **Gold standard:** Performance was validated against a gold-standard corpus of 20 Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews (CDSR) published in 2025, spanning diverse medical domains (cardiology, oncology, infectious diseases, mental health, etc.). The included-study PMIDs from each review (total N = 585) served as ground truth. Review-level topic metadata and search deadlines are provided in Supplementary Material 1, file 1.1; benchmarking retrieval results are provided in Supplementary Material 2, file 2.1.
- **Standardized input:** For each CDSR review, the research topic was taken from the review abstract's Objective statement, corresponding to the "Prompt in Pubchat" column in Supplementary Material 1, file 1.1. The CDSR-specific literature search cutoff date is listed in the "Search_deadline" column of the same file. Tool-specific input methods: PubChat received this objective-derived topic text and a year cutoff filter; Consensus, Elicit and ASTA received the same topic text with the search deadline noted; ChatGPT, Gemini, Grok, Qwen, and Perplexity received the full structured prompt template (Part 2), with the objective-derived topic inserted into the [Research Topic] field and the search deadline inserted into the [YYYY/MM-DD] field.
- **Search deadline:** A literature search cutoff date was enforced for each CDSR review to match the temporal scope of the original Cochrane search. The specific cutoff date for each CDSR review is provided in Supplementary Material 1, file 1.1 ("Search_deadline" column). The enforcement method for each tool is described in the Standardized input section above.

1.2 Tool Characteristics and Evaluation Paradigms

Based on each tool's interaction paradigm, the 11 configurations of 9 tools follow three distinct evaluation protocols.

PubChat (3 retrieval modes)

PubChat is the system under evaluation. It employs a multi-phase autonomous architecture (see main text Fig. 1) that anchors all retrieval to the PubMed E-utilities API, using LLMs solely for query generation and relevance scoring rather than reference generation. Three retrieval modes correspond to different relevance score thresholds applied to the same underlying retrieval pool.

Implementation availability: A containerized public release of PubChat is available at https://github.com/PubChatOfficial/PubChat_smart_literature_search. The repository provides deployment materials to support external installation and workflow reproduction.

Mode	Relevance Threshold	Score Range Included	Characteristic
PubChat-Broad	Score >= 1	Scores 1, 2, and 3	Maximum recall; includes mildly relevant articles
PubChat-Standard	Score >= 2	Scores 2 and 3	Balanced precision-recall; excludes mildly relevant
PubChat-Core	Score = 3	Score 3 only	Maximum precision; highly relevant articles only

Deep Research LLMs + Perplexity (5 tools)

These tools accept a natural-language prompt and return a narrative prose response with embedded citations. The user-facing interaction is identical across all five: a free-text input field produces unstructured text output requiring post-processing to extract individual references. Note: Perplexity is a search-augmented retrieval tool, not a large language model, but is evaluated alongside the LLMs because its output format (narrative prose rather than structured citation tables) requires the same structured extraction prompt and post-processing pipeline.

Tool	Model / Version	Mode	Access Platform
ChatGPT	GPT-5.2-Thinking	Deep Research	https://chatgpt.com
Gemini	Gemini-3.0-Pro	Deep Research	https://gemini.google.com
Grok	Grok-4.1-Thinking	DeepSearch	https://grok.com
Qwen	Qwen3-Max	Deep Research	https://chat.qwen.ai
Perplexity	Sonar	Deep Research	https://perplexity.ai

Specialized Retrieval Tools (3 tools)

These tools are purpose-built for academic literature retrieval and natively output structured citation lists with metadata fields (title, authors, journal, year). No prompt engineering is required to extract individual references.

Tool	Mode / Settings	Output Format	Retrieval Limit
Elicit (https://elicit.com)	"Find Papers" mode; top 300 displayed	Structured list with relevance labels	Top 300 papers; "not relevant" / "not mentioned" excluded
ASTA (https://asta.allen.ai/)	"Find Papers" mode; 3-tier relevance	Structured list: "perfectly relevant", "relevant", "somewhat relevant"	All relevance tiers included
Consensus AI (https://consensus.app)	Deep mode; year cutoff filter applied	Structured citation list	Maximum 50 papers (system limitation)

1.3 Evaluation Protocols

PubChat Protocol (Broad, Standard, Core)

- **Input:** The standardized research question and search deadline were entered into the PubChat tool.
- **Processing:** PubChat executes its autonomous multi-phase architecture (see main text Fig. 1): Phase I generates five-level relevance scoring criteria from the research question using Gemini-Flash-Latest; Phase II performs multi-round iterative PubMed retrieval with a five-stage dynamic search strategy, two-stage screening (embedding pre-filter + LLM scoring with three-round verification), and data enrichment.
- **Output:** A structured Excel workbook containing all retrieved articles information with relevance scores (ranging from 1 to 3), bibliometric metadata (Journal Impact Factor, JCR quartile, CAS partition), PMIDs and etc. The three retrieval modes are derived by applying different score thresholds to this single output: Broad (scores ≥ 1), Standard (scores ≥ 2), Core (score = 3).
- **Configuration: PubChat was configured with default parameters for the benchmarking study. For the validation benchmark, the system ran 50 maximum retrieval rounds and used a target of 300 articles per review. Eight languages were tested for the cross-linguistic consistency analysis.**

LLMs + Perplexity Protocol (ChatGPT, Gemini, Grok, Qwen, Perplexity)

- **Input:** The full structured prompt (Part 2 of this document) was provided to each model. The prompt assigns the role of "Systematic Review Information Specialist" and instructs the LLM to perform iterative search with term expansion, targeting maximum recall.
- **Prompt customization:** The standardized research question (from Supplementary Material 2, file 2.1) was inserted into the [Research Topic] field. The CDSR-specific literature search cutoff date was inserted into the [YYYY/MM-DD] field.
- **Output:** Each LLM generated a narrative review text (Part 1 of the prompt output) with numerical superscript citations, followed by a structured references table (Part 2) containing: No., Journal Name, Article Title, Publication Date, and First Author.
- **Post-processing:** Article titles from the LLM-generated references table were batch-imported into PubMed to obtain PMIDs. Each reference was then classified into one of four tiers: (1) Valid PMID (indexed in MEDLINE/PubMed), (2) Non-PubMed (Embase/Scopus-exclusive), (3) Non-Academic (websites, blogs, promotional materials), and (4) Hallucination (fabricated references with no verifiable source).
- **Mode settings:** All five LLMs were tested in their respective advanced research modes (Deep Research or DeepSearch), which enable multi-step web search, iterative refinement, and extended context windows. Models were instructed to continue searching until no new relevant papers could be identified.
- **Access method:** Each model was accessed via its official web interface. No API-level access was used for the comparator LLMs. The prompt was entered as a single message in a new conversation thread for each of the 20 CDSR reviews.

Specialized Retrieval Tools Protocol (Elicit, ASTA, Consensus)

- **Input:** The standardized research question text was entered directly into each tool's native search interface. No complex prompt engineering was required, as these tools are designed to accept research questions in natural language and return structured citation lists.

- **Output:** Each tool natively outputs a structured literature list with metadata fields (title, authors, journal, year, and in some cases relevance labels). PMIDs were extracted directly from the output or obtained by batch-importing titles into PubMed.

Elicit (<https://elicit.com>): "Find Papers" mode was selected. The top 300 papers displayed by the platform were collected. Papers labeled as "not relevant" or "not mentioned" in Elicit's AI-generated summary were excluded. The remaining papers were counted as retrieved by Elicit. The research question and search deadline were provided as input.

ASTA (<https://asta.allen.ai>): "Find Papers" mode was selected. ASTA automatically classifies retrieved papers into three relevance tiers: "perfectly relevant", "relevant", and "somewhat relevant". All papers from all three relevance tiers were included in the retrieval count, with no exclusions.

Consensus AI (<https://consensus.app>): Deep mode was enabled with a year cutoff filter applied to match the CDSR search deadline. Due to inherent system limitations, Consensus could retrieve a maximum of 50 papers per query. All returned papers were included in the retrieval count.

1.4 Standardization Measures

The following measures were implemented to ensure fair and reproducible comparison across all 11 configurations among 9 tools:

- **Identical research topics:** All tools received the same objective-derived research topic for each CDSR review. For ChatGPT, Gemini, Grok, Qwen, and Perplexity, this topic was inserted into the fixed "Systematic Review Information Specialist" prompt template; PubChat and specialized retrieval tools received the same topic text via their native input interfaces.
- **Uniform search deadline:** The literature search cutoff date from each Cochrane review was enforced as a constraint for all tools, either via the platform filters (PubChat), prompt template (ChatGPT, Gemini, Grok, Qwen, Perplexity) or query text annotation (Consensus, Elicit, ASTA).
- **Systematic reference classification:** All retrieved references from every tool underwent the same four-tier classification: Valid PMID (indexed in MEDLINE/PubMed), Non-PubMed (Embase/Scopus-exclusive), Non-Academic (websites, blogs, promotional materials), and Hallucination (fabricated references). Titles were batch-imported into PubMed to verify existence and obtain PMIDs.
- **Deduplication:** Duplicate PMIDs within each tool's results were removed prior to metric calculation.
- **Gold-standard scoring:** Retrieved PMIDs were matched against Cochrane gold-standard included-study PMIDs to determine true positives, false positives, and false negatives. Metrics calculated included Precision, Recall, F1-Score, F2-Score (beta = 2, prioritizing recall), normalized Discounted Cumulative Gain (nDCG) for ranking quality, and Source Fidelity (proportion of references with verified PubMed IDs).
- **Journal quality assessment:** Journal quality was assessed by JCR quartile distribution for all retrieved articles across all tools, enabling comparison of the bibliometric quality profile of each tool's retrieval set.

1.5 Reference Classification Protocol

All references retrieved by all tools underwent a standardized four-tier classification process to quantify source fidelity and hallucination rates:

Tier	Classification	Definition
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1	Valid PMID	Article is indexed in MEDLINE/PubMed with a verifiable PMID
2	Non-PubMed	Article exists but is indexed exclusively in Embase, Scopus, or other databases (not PubMed)
3	Non-Academic	Reference points to a website, blog, press release, promotional material, or other non-peer-reviewed source
4	Hallucination	Reference is fabricated: no verifiable source exists matching the provided title, authors, or journal

Note: PubChat achieves 100% Source Fidelity (all Tier 1) by design, as it retrieves exclusively from the PubMed E-utilities API and uses LLMs solely for query generation and relevance scoring rather than reference generation. For PubChat, Tiers 2-4 are structurally avoided in the retrieved output because all records are obtained from PubMed E-utilities and verified by PMID.

Part 2: LLM Prompt Template ("Systematic Review Information Specialist")

The following fixed prompt template was used for ChatGPT, Gemini, Grok, Qwen, and Perplexity. For each of the 20 CDSR reviews, the [Research Topic] placeholder was replaced with the objective-derived topic text from the CDSR abstract, and the [YYYY/MM-DD] placeholder was replaced with the corresponding literature search cutoff date. The prompt was entered as a single message in a new conversation thread. Note: This template was not used for PubChat, Elicit, ASTA, or Consensus, which accept simple query text via their native interfaces.

Role: Systematic Review Information Specialist

Primary Objective

Your single most important goal is to achieve **MAXIMUM POSSIBLE RECALL** of academic literature for the topic and date specified. Your performance is judged on the comprehensiveness of the final references table.

Mandatory Protocol

- **Internal Strategy:** Deconstruct the topic into core concepts. Generate an exhaustive list of search terms (including synonyms, MeSH terms, variations). Formulate multiple, complex Boolean search queries.
- **Iterative Search:** Use your online search tools to execute the queries. **DO NOT STOP** after finding a few relevant articles. Persistently modify, broaden, and refine your search terms based on initial findings to uncover more papers. Use keywords from relevant articles to launch **new search rounds**. This iterative process is critical.
- **Synthesize & Compile:** After an exhaustive search, write a concise review citing your findings with numerical superscripts. Then, compile the complete references table.

Input

- **Research Topic:** [Research topic]
- **Literature Search Cutoff Date:** [YYYY/MM-DD]

Core Constraints

- **Direct Output:** Start the response directly with the review text. No plan or introduction.
- **Time Constraint:** All cited literature MUST be published on or before the cutoff date.
- **Data Honesty:** All reference metadata MUST be real and accurate. No fabrication.
- **Output Structure:** Strictly follow the two-part structure below.

Output Requirements

Part 1: Generated Review Text

[Your response starts directly here with the review containing superscript citations.]

Part 2: References Table

List all unique references cited, corresponding to the citation number.

No.	Journal Name	Article Title	Publication Date (YYYY-MM-DD)	First Author
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